

Digitisation of Existing Buildings with Arbitrary Shaped Spaces from Point Clouds

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ABSTRACT

Digital Twins for buildings can significantly reduce building operation costs. However, existing methods for constructing geometric digital twins fail to model the complex geometry of indoor environments. To address this problem, this paper proposes a novel method for digitising building geometry with arbitrary shapes of spaces by detecting empty regions in point clouds and then expanding them to occupy the entire indoor space. The detected spaces are then used to detect structural objects and transition between spaces, such as doors, without assuming their geometric properties. The method reconstructs the volumetric representation of individual spaces, detects walls, windows and doors between them and splits the PCD into point clusters of individual spaces from large-scale cluttered PCDs of complex environments. We conduct extensive experiments on S3DIS and TUMCMS datasets and show that the proposed method outperforms existing methods for digitising Manhattan-world buildings. In contrast to existing approaches, the method allows digitising buildings with arbitrarily shaped spaces, including complex layouts, non-flat, non-vertical walls, and non-flat, non-horizontal floors and ceilings.

INTRODUCTION

Digital Twins (DTs) of buildings are digital replicas of existing physical assets. Building DTs have shown their importance in the operation and management stages of the building life cycle (Sacks et al. 2018; Ozturk 2021; Lu et al. 2021). However, most existing buildings were built before the emergence of CAD, BIM, or DTs and lack 3D digital models for as-built states. Practitioners report that costs and time remain substantial barriers to the broader adoption of DTs for existing buildings (Enterprises 2020). Bridging this gap can potentially add up to 250 billion dollars annually worldwide (Institute 2017). Modelling geometric information from Point Cloud Data (PCD) provides a promising solution for geometry digitization.

Digitisation of the geometry of existing buildings means generating a 3D model of DT geometry. This process includes acquiring measurements from the real world and using them to model the geometry of the asset. There are multiple approaches to capturing geometry, including videogrammetry, mobile laser scanning and static laser scanning, in the increasing order of the acquisition costs. However, the level of error for photogrammetry remains higher than for mobile laser scanning (Agostinho et al. 2022), while the latter remains higher than for static laser scanning (Trzeciak and Brilakis 2021). Moreover, the level of error and density of measurements for mobile solutions remains insufficient for various use-cases of DTs, especially for distances larger than 5 metres (Trzeciak and Brilakis 2021). Therefore, digitisation of geometry from laser-scanned PCDs is the only available solution for many buildings. It assumes capturing a large-scale PCD of as-is building conditions, which may contain no imagery or sequential data.

The construction of geometric DTs of existing assets from PCD remains expensive and time-consuming, thus unprofitable for the industry. It still heavily relies on manual modelling, even though several automatic and semi-automatic tools have been developed over time (Drobnyi et al. 2023). Multiple studies show that asset modelling using state-of-the-art software still requires enormous manual hours for buildings (Qu et al. 2014; Pan et al. 2023), industrial assets (Agapaki et al. 2018), bridges (Lu and Brilakis 2019), among other examples. The costs of digitising existing buildings do not counter the benefits of DTs for the operation and maintenance stages currently. As

52 a result, the overall productivity of the building management is reduced, entailing higher costs on
53 asset operation (Institute 2017).

54 The majority of existing methods and tools for digitising the geometry of existing buildings
55 have traditionally focused on digitising structures with simple shapes and patterns characterised
56 by flat surfaces, right angles, and uniform dimensions (Drobnyi et al. 2023). While the geometry
57 of some buildings falls into this category, many buildings have more complex geometry. For
58 example, many standard residential buildings in the UK have attic, non-Manhattan bay or dormer
59 windows (NHBC 2016), shown in Figure 2. In addition, digitising such parts of buildings requires
60 disproportionately high manual effort because of the complexity of the input and lack of tools
61 supporting complex environments. Therefore, there is an urge for automatic tools for digitising
62 assets with non-standard patterns, sophisticated boundaries and the presence of clutter. Such tools
63 have the potential to reduce the manual effort in digitising existing facilities and reducing the costs
64 of DT for the building in operation. This can improve the overall management of buildings and
65 trimming operational overheads.

66 The geometry of any building consists of objects and spaces, which are essential for multiple
67 applications. For instance, objects and their geometries are important for predictive maintenance,
68 quality monitoring, and renovation (Motawa and Almarshad 2013; Nummelin et al. 2011; Anil
69 et al. 2013; Badenko et al. 2018). Spaces are important for activity management, energy and sound
70 simulations, and behavioural simulations (Rahmani Asl et al. 2015; McArthur 2015; Sanhudo et al.
71 2018; Chen et al. 2018). This paper presents a novel approach to digitising the indoor geometry
72 of existing buildings from large-scale PCDs with an emphasis on space reconstruction. The main
73 goal is to detect 3D Euclidian space of individual indoor spaces, to split the input PCD into point
74 clusters of individual spaces, and to detect objects that separate them. The method analyses empty
75 blobs within the 3D space as a basis for room (or other spaces) detection. In this way, the proposed
76 method is able to detect spaces, such as rooms, offices, hallways, among others, with arbitrary
77 shapes, including spaces with arbitrarily orientated or curved walls and varying or slanted ceilings
78 (Figure 1). It then detects objects between adjacent spaces, such as walls, and transitions between

spaces, such as doors and windows. It allows obtaining a 3D navigable map of the buildings. Lastly, the method also preserves the exact geometry of the PCDs. The contributions are summarised as follows:

- We propose a geometry digitisation method that can deal with arbitrary shapes of spaces.
- We analyse empty regions of the 3D space and the geometry of their pair-wise boundaries.
- We conduct extensive experiments on Stanford3D S3DIS and TUMCMS datasets to validate the proposed method's effectiveness.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: the research background is covered in section 2; the proposed method and every step is presented in section 3; the experiments and the evaluation of the method are shown in section 4, followed by the discussion in section 5 and conclusion and the future work in section 6.

BACKGROUND

This section discusses the state-of-the-art in digitising building geometry, including space detection and modelling from large-scale indoor PCDs. It starts with a brief overview of the 2D methods (top-down view) for building digitisation from PCDs, followed by the 3D methods and object detection methods. Then, it highlights methods used for other data sources, such as images and scanner locations. At the end, the section summarises the advantages and limitations of current methods and states Gaps in Knowledge (GiK).

The first type of approach attempted to reduce the problem into the *2D domain* and infer space and object locations from 2D. For instance, Ochmann et al. detected planar surfaces and projected them onto the X-Y plane and obtained an oversegmentation of the space (Ochmann et al. 2019). They then used Integer Linear Programming (ILP) to merge spaces in 2D to obtain the 2D space arrangement, which was then used to build a 3D model of a building. Another example used a horizontal slice of a PCD that contained the ceiling to obtain 2D space arrangement (Macher et al. 2017). This method assumes that spaces had disjoint ceiling surfaces.

Several methods are based on a similar approach. RANSAC (Anagnostopoulos et al. 2016a;

105 Anagnostopoulos et al. 2016b; Wang et al. 2017), Hough Transform (Oesau et al. 2013) or region-
106 growing (Mura et al. 2014; Xiong et al. 2013; Nikoohemat et al. 2020; Tang et al. 2022; Bassier
107 and Vergauwen 2020) methods are used to detect planar patches in 3D or line segments in 2D.
108 The object and space detection is then solved in the X-Y plane through optimisation or graph
109 techniques (Nikoohemat et al. 2020; Xiong et al. 2013; Monszpart et al. 2015). This group of
110 methods can detect spaces with arbitrarily orientated walls, assuming they are sufficiently visible
111 in the PCD. Still, they cannot deal with ceilings of varying heights and are sensitive to clutter and
112 occlusions because they are based on plane detection methods, such as RANSAC. Additionally, the
113 computational costs of RANSAC and Hough Transform rise exponentially when the input becomes
114 larger.

115 Newer methods try to digitise the geometry directly in *3D space* to overcome these issues and
116 account for the 3D variations in the environment. Tran et al. proposed to split the 3D space along
117 three main axes on peaks of point histograms and then merge cuboids to form spaces, walls and
118 slabs based on the shape-grammar approach (Tran et al. 2018). They reconstructed a 3D volumetric
119 model with spaces, but all walls and room boundaries were parallel to one of the three orientations.
120 In addition, they require manual modelling for room transitions. A similar approach was employed
121 in (Murali et al. 2017).

122 An automatic void-growing approach selected a seed point and grew a cuboid to detect empty
123 parts of PCDs as rooms (Pan et al. 2023). After that, they merged overlapping regions to model L-
124 and U-shaped spaces. This, however, has a similar limitation and does not allow modelling spaces
125 with boundaries not parallel to one of the three main directions. Hüber et al. also reconstructed 3D
126 space arrangement by detecting walls on edges of ceilings (Hübner et al. 2021). They voxelised the
127 input scene, classified each voxel and provided interior voxel clustering of the space. Their method
128 can deal with non-Manhattan environments, assuming limited floor, ceiling and wall orientation
129 variations.

130 Deep learning-based methods do not require any prior knowledge about the environment (Tang
131 et al. 2022) in contrast to the abovementioned methods. Mehranfar et al. used semantic segmenta-

132 tion to extract wall, ceiling, and floor points and extract 2D ceiling clusters disjointed by wall points
133 to obtain a 2D arrangement. Some approaches use *deep neural networks* (NNs) on PCDs and
134 images to model the 2D space arrangement. For example, Liu et al. used NNs to infer room corners
135 on the X-Y plane directly from PCDs (Liu et al. 2018). They then used ILP to compute polygons
136 of rooms. Another example used image-based NN to predict floorplans from PCD projection on
137 the X-Y plane (Chen et al. 2019). Wu et al. used a similar approach by projecting only statistics
138 about min/max/occupancy height over a pillar of point in the same X-Y locations (Wu et al. 2023).
139 These methods remain prone to errors and require more data to generalise to buildings with other
140 construction practices and patterns.

141 A few methods use NNs to infer objects directly from PCD. Some propose advanced methods
142 for semantic segmentation of PCDs of indoor to be used instead of RANSAC, region growing, etc.,
143 to alleviate their shortcomings (Perez-Perez et al. 2021a; Perez-Perez et al. 2021b). Others use NNs
144 to produce bounding boxes of structural objects and furniture from room-scale PCDs (Xu et al.
145 2021a; Xu et al. 2021b). The main benefit of learning-based approaches is their ability to capture
146 arbitrary objects and spaces subject to the availability of sufficiently large labelled datasets. The
147 applicability of these methods in large-scale and cluttered environments, however, remains limited.

148 At last, we review methods that use *information other than PCD* to detect and model building
149 geometry. Videogrammetry provides a PCD or a mesh from a sequence of images. Therefore, it can
150 exploit image-based semantic and instance segmentation methods and impose these results onto the
151 produced output in 3D, exploiting the superiority of image-based methods over PCD-based ones.
152 In addition, it provides a sequence of sensor locations that can help infer spaces and objects from
153 PCDs. For example, Hydra used scanner locations from visual odometry to estimate what scans
154 had been taken in the same room (Hughes et al. 2022). They used the Euclidean signed distance
155 function to disjoint scanner locations from different rooms. They then used this information to
156 obtain what scanner locations were from the same room and superimposed this information during
157 their videogrammetry. Another example of this approach is Kimera (Rosinol et al. 2021).

158 Summarising the state-of-the-art literature and *Gaps in Knowledge*, there is no method for 3D

159 volumetric reconstruction of indoor environments that can deal with clutter and arbitrary geometry
160 of spaces from large-scale PCDs without other information, such as images and scanner locations.
161 This is important to establish because many DT applications require a density and a margin of error
162 that can only be captured by laser scanners. Their typical output may not contain data other than a
163 PCD. The existing methods of digitising geometry of existing buildings from PCDs are either based
164 on the planar detection method and can only reason about spaces in 2D, therefore, cannot deal with
165 varying 3D details, or use strong assumptions about the environment, such as Manhattan-world
166 assumption, to deal with spaces in 3D. The existing methods either cannot deal with varying height
167 ceilings, non-vertical 3D boundaries, and non-perpendicular walls or require other sources of data
168 as input. Clutter and occlusions remain challenging for surface detection-based methods, especially
169 those based on plane detection, such as RANSAC-based methods. We do not know how to deal
170 with arbitrary-shaped spaces in large-scale and cluttered PCDs of indoor environments.

171 **PROPOSED SOLUTION**

172 We design our method to detect spaces, such as rooms, corridors, and halls, of arbitrary shapes
173 to tackle the above-mentioned challenges directly from PCD. The proposed method receives an
174 indoor PCD of a building and produces spaces as sets of voxels in 3D space and locations of walls
175 and doorways as oriented bounding boxes for further modelling. The voxelisation of the output is
176 selected beforehand and can be arbitrary.

177 The method is based on the idea that any space is an empty PCD region far from any point.
178 Therefore, the method extracts empty parts of the PCD and then expands them to "touch" space
179 boundaries and other spaces. Lastly, it uses volumetric spaces to detect transitions between them,
180 namely doors and windows, and separating objects, such as walls, ceilings, and floors. Figure 3
181 provides an overview of the proposed method.

182 **Void detection**

183 The core idea is that spaces have massive parts (in comparison with objects) with no points
184 in the middle. Therefore, the method begins with detecting empty parts of the 3D space that are
185 far from any point of the input PCD. We compute an Euclidean distance function (EDF) for the

186 PCD first (Equation 1). Figure 4 shows an example of the distance function for the 2D case. The
 187 distance function is then thresholded to obtain all parts of the 3D space that are far from any point
 188 in the PCD (Equation 2).

$$189 \quad D_{PCD}(x, y, z) = \min_{(X_p, Y_p, Z_p) \in PCD} \|(x, y, z) - (X_p, Y_p, Z_p)\|_2 \quad (1)$$

$$190 \quad C = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 | D(x, y, z) > \theta\} \quad (2)$$

191 The threshold is selected so empty regions of different spaces are separated as we need to
 192 differentiate between them. Therefore, the threshold is set to be larger than half the width of a door
 193 but smaller than that of a narrow room. As a result, the thresholded set of empty regions is disjoint
 194 because every point in the doorway is sufficiently close to some point of the PCD.

195 However, such an approach cannot deal with narrow corridors that are slightly wider than a
 196 typical door due to noise and clutter. Therefore, we employ a two-scale empty space detection.
 197 This means that we detect empty space in the remaining part of the PCD after detecting empty
 198 space with the above-mentioned threshold. We achieve this by computing the second EDF for the
 199 detected empty space ($D_{ES}(x, y, z)$). We then combine them by computing a weighted minimum
 200 between the two EDFs (Equation 3). The parameter λ is necessary to balance the different nature
 201 of the two EDFs. This allows the detection of empty parts of narrow corridors.

$$202 \quad D_\lambda(x, y, z) = \min(D_{PCD}(x, y, z), \lambda * D_{ES}(x, y, z)) \quad (3)$$

203 We use DBSCAN clustering on 3D coordinates to split it into multiple parts for individual
 204 spaces after identifying an empty part of the PCD. We further refer to them as seeds for space
 205 detection. We ensure that each seed belongs to a single space by choosing a threshold larger than
 206 a typical transition between spaces. These seeds are then expanded.

207 Void Expansion

208 The seeds cover only those parts of the PCD that are far from any point. However, we aim to
209 detect all space inside rooms and corridors. Therefore, we expand each seed to occupy the entire
210 empty space. We achieve it by iteratively expanding each seed to cover all surrounding space with
211 the EDF slightly smaller than the current smallest value for the seed. Equation 4 shows an update
212 step for void expansion, where V_j^i is the j -th void on i -th iteration, α is the maximum expansion
213 distance on one iteration and θ_i is a EDF threshold on i -th iteration ($\forall i : \theta_i < \theta_{i-1}$). We gradually
214 decrease the threshold to 0 to cover the entire space. In this step, other clusters of voids prevent a
215 particular void from leaving a room through an opened door, for example.

$$216 \begin{aligned} V_j^i = \{ & (x, y, z) : \\ & \min_{(X_v, Y_v, Z_v) \in V_j^{i-1}} \|(x, y, z) - (X_v, Y_v, Z_v)\|_2 < \alpha, \\ & D_{PCD}(x, y, z) < \theta_i \} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

217 The proposed approach for detecting voids in a PCD cannot penetrate regions between the floor
218 and furniture, such as chairs and tables. Therefore, we extend each void to the floor level along the
219 Z axis. The floor level for each is the 0.025 quantile of a PCD in the same XY area of the void. The
220 0.025 quantile is a valid approximation if there are some visible points on the floor with or without
221 the presence of a noise. The result of this step is the final void for each room.

222 Transition Detection

223 The obtained voids occupy all space of rooms inside the PCD and represent the internal space for
224 each room, and provide 3D space decomposition for the building. In the next step, we need to detect
225 transitions between these steps. We compute the distance between each pair of voids (Equation 5)
226 and record every pair that has this distance close to zero (smaller than a wall thickness). This means
227 that two voids are touching each other, and there is a transition between them. We then recover
228 the profile of their transition as a set of points from both voids that are closer to each other than a

229 threshold (Equation 6). The threshold depends on the voxelisation of the output (e.g. one voxel
 230 size).

$$231 \quad D(V_i, V_j) = \min_{X \in V_i, Y \in V_j} \|X - Y\|_2 \quad (5)$$

$$232 \quad T_{ij} = \{X : X \in V_i, \min_{Y \in V_j} \|X - Y\|_2 < \beta\}$$

$$233 \quad \cup \{Y : Y \in V_j, \min_{X \in V_i} \|X - Y\|_2 < \beta\} \quad (6)$$

234 The nature of the void detection steps implies that multiple voids can be detected inside a single
 235 space if this space is narrow or heavily occluded. Therefore, each transition generally falls into
 236 one of the two cases: a transition between two spaces, such as a door or a window; or two voids
 237 belonging to the same space due to multiple seeds detected in a single room. We craft a set of rules
 238 based on the geometric parameters of the profile to differentiate between these cases.

239 First, we compute the height (along the Z axis), width (the largest variance on the XY plane)
 240 and depth (the smallest variance on the XY plane) of the oriented bounding box of the profile,
 241 together with the distance between the lowest point of the profile and the floor (Z-lowest) (Figure 5).
 242 The transition is then classified through these four features using a set of crafted rules. We detect
 243 a door or window if two of the dimensions are close to a typical door or window profile. We
 244 detect a transition inside a room if the three dimensions are large or the height dimension is large.
 245 These voids are then merged. As a result, the 3D space decomposition is enriched with transitions
 246 represented by doors (navigable) and windows (not navigable).

247 **Wall Detection and PCD clustering**

248 We extract space separators, such as walls, using a similar approach. We compute the distance
 249 between each pair of voids and extract space parts close to each other (Equation 6). In this step, the
 250 threshold parameter β is selected to be slightly larger than the width of the thickest wall. Therefore,
 251 it extracts only a boundary of a void close to another.

252 The extracted location indicates a rough location of a wall. The bounding box is then enlarged
 253 to capture more context and deal with clutter. The resulting extended bounding box contains a wall.

254 We extract a point cluster from the original PCD for each void on the last step of the method.
255 Each point of the PCD is assigned the label of the closest voxel from the set of voids using a
256 KD-tree. We then use them to classify each point as on top, bottom, side or inside of the void. The
257 top points represent the ceiling, lamps and other objects attached to a ceiling; the bottom points
258 represent the floor; the side points represent walls, columns, beams and furniture attached to walls;
259 and the inside points represent only furniture. We also refer to assigning point cluster IDs to each
260 point as a segmentation of the PCD based on the spaces.

261 **EXPERIMENTS**

262 We chose Python 3.8 to implement the proposed method. We used the following libraries:
263 Numpy (Harris et al. 2020) for mathematics, Scipy (Virtanen et al. 2020) and Sklearn (Pedregosa
264 et al. 2011) for spatial algorithms, such as DBSCAN clustering and Kd trees, Open3D (Zhou et al.
265 2018) for 3D visualisation. We chose these libraries because they are efficient and well-documented
266 solutions to our needs. We used a computer with AMD Ryzen 5 5600X CPU, Nvidia GTX 2070
267 Super GPU, 32GB RAM for the experiments.

268 We conduct the experiments on Stanford 3D S3DIS dataset (Armeni et al. 2016) to validate the
269 effectiveness of our proposed method, which is expected to handle large-scale and occluded point
270 clouds. The dataset contains six point clouds representing six storeys of multiple buildings in the
271 US and covers more than 6000 square metres of area. These point clouds are highly cluttered and
272 large-scale. In addition, we evaluate our method on TUMCMS dataset (Pan et al. 2023), which
273 consists of one storey of a university building in Germany.

274 We provide quantitative evaluation for the transition detection, wall detection, PCD room-based
275 clustering and manual modelling reduction. We also provide qualitative evaluation for the other
276 steps and the method’s overall performance.

277 **Void detection**

278 First, we show the results for the first step of the approach. We use 7.5cm voxel sizes to balance
279 precision and computational efficiency. Figure 6 (a) shows the space further away from any point

280 than 85cm. The 85cm threshold has been chosen because it is slightly larger than half of the door
281 width in this dataset. This threshold can be adjusted according to the dataset if necessary.

282 It is clearly seen that the method identifies the insides of all rooms; however, it struggles to
283 detect narrow corridors. Reducing the threshold leads to the connection of voids from neighbouring
284 rooms because they have wide doors. Therefore, multi-scale void detection is used to deal with
285 narrow corridors. Figure 6 (b) shows the empty space detected with a decreased threshold but also
286 further from the already detected empty space. Here, narrow corridors are also detected.

287 Lastly, we cluster the extracted empty space using DBSCAN with the distance threshold pro-
288 portional to the voxel size. Figure 7 (a) further shows the clusters obtained from the empty space.
289 The first observation is that the large room on the top left corner is connected to the corridor. This
290 is because there is no door but a free passage (from the floor to the ceiling) that is around 5 metres
291 wide. Therefore, the algorithm treats it as the same space.

292 The second observation is that narrow spaces, such as corridors or narrow rooms, are sometimes
293 oversegmented. This highlights the importance of transition detection and transition classification
294 in the later stages of the method.

295 **Void expansion**

296 The voids are expanded after being detected in the previous step. Figure 7 (b) shows the
297 results of the void expansion on the same scene. The ceiling is removed for visualisation purposes,
298 and only light fixtures remain on top of the voids. The figure shows that the proposed method can
299 successfully grow the voids to the point where all space inside rooms is occupied and the boundaries
300 of the voids lie on PCD and connection to other voids. It is also seen that the boundaries of voids
301 connected to neighbouring rooms lie in the door passages, which was desired.

302 Figure 8 further provides examples of non-trivial boundaries of spaces. It shows that the pro-
303 posed method can identify voids of arbitrary shapes and can successfully deal with non-Manhattan
304 and non-convex spaces with non-straight (curved) boundaries. Figure 9 further shows that the
305 proposed method can successfully deal with spaces with complex ceiling shapes. It includes
306 variable-height horizontal ceilings and tilted ceilings.

Transition and wall detection

The transition detection, i.e. detecting when the boundaries of two voids touch each other, accomplishes its goal and detects all transitions correctly. This includes all doors, windows, and transitions inside a single room.

In the next step, each transition is classified based on its shape and dimensions. We assign one of two classes: inside a single space (for oversegmented rooms, example Figure 10 a) and the boundary between two rooms (a door or a window, example Figure 10 b). The latter can then be differentiated based on its dimensions and Z-level (the bottom of a door should be on the floor level).

The experiments of the proposed classification method show high performance in classifying the transactions. Table 1 and Table 2 show the performance in terms of precision and recall (Equation 7) of the classification step for doors/windows and transitions between voids that belong to the same space, respectively. The precision and recall are chosen as widely used metrics for classification tasks, and they provide insights into what percentage of target objects are correctly classified (recall) and what percentage of classified objects are indeed from the target class (precision). The voids with the latter transitions are then merged. After merging, We discard doors/windows connecting the same void because such detections are incorrect.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}; R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}; IoU = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

The method surpasses the 90 per cent threshold on the majority of the scenes. The 100 per cent precision on connecting voids of the same space ensures that none of the spaces are under-segmented due to the incorrect classification of the transitions. The method tends to classify border cases in transition classification in favour of doors/windows because removing them is easier than separating spaces manually.

Most false positive door/window detection comes from narrow and heavily cluttered parts of PCDs. It introduces over-segmentation during void detection and expansion steps. The transitions

332 between them are small due to the clutter. Therefore, these transitions are misclassified as their local
333 geometry is more typical of doors or windows. These two factors contribute to lower door/window
334 detection precision on the TUMCMS dataset.

335 Table 3 provides wall detection performance for the two datasets. The main source of false
336 positives in wall detection is the over-segmentation in some narrow and heavily cluttered spaces,
337 similar to door/window detection. Additionally, rooms that share only a corner but not a wall
338 trigger false positive wall detections (Figure 11).

339 **Space decomposition and PCD clustering**

340 Next, we cluster the input PCD into point clusters of individual rooms by performing a KNN
341 classification based on voids. In other words, we assign each point to the closest void. Figure 12
342 shows the result for the Area 1 of S3DIS dataset.

343 We further evaluate space decomposition by computing the Intersection over Union (IoU,
344 Equation 7) between the detection and the ground truth PCD of spaces. Figure 13 shows what
345 fraction of spaces have higher IoU for different thresholds for the S3DIS dataset, excluding corridors
346 because corridors. The graph shows that over 80 per cent of detected spaces have at least 90 per cent
347 IoU with the ground truth.

348 We also evaluate our approach's space detection performance on the TUMCMS dataset. We
349 compute the average IoU for points on the floor between the predicted and the ground truth labels
350 (Table 4). Our method outperforms other methods designed to detect volumetric spaces in PCDs.

351 **Application case study**

352 Lastly, we evaluate how the proposed method impacts geometry modelling from PCD. We
353 selected a part of the TUMCMS dataset and modelled floors, ceilings, walls, doors, windows,
354 and columns, and we built 2D floorplans to model spaces. We used assisting tools that help
355 fit geometric primitives to model the geometry of individual objects and spaces, following the
356 approaches presented in commercial software for building geometry modelling from PCDs. This
357 included fitting cuboidal objects by selecting 3 points to derive the object's location, orientation
358 and dimensions and using a 2D polygon drawing tool to draw floorplans.

359 We compared two scenarios: using just these tools to model the specified objects and using
360 our method to extract point clusters for objects with the subsequent modelling with the same tools.
361 Floors, ceilings and columns were modelled similarly for both scenarios, and no improvement was
362 observed. For the remainder of the objects, the extraction of point clusters for objects significantly
363 reduced the modelling time because the extracted cluster was small and did not contain many
364 irrelevant points for a particular object. As a result, we observed a 67.2 per cent reduction in the
365 total modelling time for these objects.

366 Lastly, floorplan generation was automatically computed using our method by projecting 3D
367 voxels of spaces onto the ground plane. This means that no manual effort was necessary for the
368 second scenario, in contrast to the manual modelling of the first scenario.

369 **DISCUSSION**

370 Overall, we showed that the proposed method achieves its goals. Specifically, it identifies spaces
371 directly from 3D PCD, detects transitions (doors) and separations (walls) between them, and splits
372 the PCD into point clusters of individual spaces. The performance of each step and the method
373 overall is very high. Additionally, the computational efficiency is high, being around 0.15 seconds
374 per square metre.

375 The proposed method does not specifically account for the noise in PCD. Although the method
376 is robust to variations in point coordinates, it assumes that no points are far off their real position.
377 This may happen when many mirrors or glass walls are in the scene. However, we observe that
378 statistical outlier removal implemented in most PCD acquisition and preprocessing software is
379 practically enough to remove such points and apply the proposed method. Both datasets used in
380 this paper did not require any additional noise handling.

381 The presented method has a few advantages over other methods for building digitisation from
382 PCD. The method is able to reconstruct buildings without assumptions about the shape of spaces
383 and objects. This means that it can successfully digitise buildings with non-flat walls and slanted
384 ceilings and floors, among other examples. For instance, Figure 9 shows that the method can
385 successfully identify areas with attics and dormer windows. It can also deal with large-scale

386 and heavily cluttered environments efficiently. Additionally, it provides a 3D navigable space
387 decomposition with the exact sizes of transitions between rooms.

388 The proposed method can capture building geometry directly from a single PCD in contrast
389 to building digitisation techniques that use videogrammetry to capture geometry, such as Kimera.
390 Therefore, the method can be used in complex environments with sophisticated shapes of spaces
391 to process data captured by mobile and static laser scanners. This may be necessary when a low
392 margin of error or high point density is necessary due to the DT’s construction requirements. No
393 specific scanning strategy is required to apply the proposed method successfully as long as visible
394 surfaces are reasonably covered and no holes larger than wide doors are presented.

395 We showed that our method outperforms recent methods for digitising Manhattan-world build-
396 ings. In contrast to (Pan et al. 2023), our method uses fewer assumptions about the environment.
397 We successfully reconstructed spaces with non-horizontal floors and ceilings, including rooms with
398 attics and staircase corridors. We also digitised spaces and detected walls that were completely
399 hidden behind bookshelves from both sides.

400 However, the voxel representation of the spaces poses some limitations on the method. A
401 large size of voxels results in suboptimal geometry with loose boundaries, while a small voxel
402 size explodes the computational complexity. It implies that the voxel size should be balanced. In
403 practice, we also split the scene into several overlapping regions along a grid, splitting the X and
404 Y axes into s parts. We then merge them after processing to reduce computational complexity.
405 Equation 8 shows the complexity of the method based on the voxel size v and the number of splits
406 along X and Y dimensions s . Also, the method assumes the doors to be open and windows to have
407 no points, which is true for laser scanning but false for RGBD cameras. In both of these cases,
408 the method will detect spaces and objects between them but will not detect doors and windows
409 between them, making them disconnected.

$$410 \quad T(v, s) = O\left(s^2 \frac{1}{vs^3}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{sv^3}\right) \quad (8)$$

411 Also, the proposed method struggles to process two types of spaces correctly. These large

412 open spaces have wide transitions with corridors (no wall or door) and very narrow and cluttered
413 small rooms, such as closets. In the former case, the method tends to undersegment spaces and
414 merge open spaces into corridors because there is no physical separation between them. In the
415 latter case, the method can over-segment space because it has multiple enclosed blobs of empty
416 space that cannot be later merged due to the small dimensions of detected transitions. We believe
417 that more flexible learning methods for transition classification can improve the method. Lastly,
418 the detected walls have only rough positions and do not represent real objects with high accuracy.
419 Further processing is necessary to derive the exact geometry of walls.

420 The method also splits a PCD into point clusters of individual spaces. This allows us to process
421 them independently in the future, reducing computational complexity. Also, many methods for
422 object detection are designed to work on room-scale PCDs. This is especially important for data-
423 driven methods, such as CorDet (Xu et al. 2021a), as their performance tends to be notably better on
424 point clusters of rooms (Qian et al. 2022). Therefore, the method proposed in this paper allows using
425 methods designed for room-scale inputs as the next step. For example, to find smaller, mechanical,
426 electrical, or furniture objects. These per-room outputs can then be automatically combined using
427 graph-based methods (Drobnyi et al. 2024) to automate geometry digitisation further. Similarly,
428 the detected bounding boxes of walls enclose real objects while not containing irrelevant parts.
429 These can also greatly simplify wall modelling for existing or future methods.

430 **CONCLUSION**

431 In conclusion, this paper presented a novel approach for digitising the geometry of existing
432 buildings. We based our method on detecting empty regions in a PCD of buildings as a basis
433 for digitisation. The method deals with spaces of arbitrary shapes. The method reconstructs the
434 volumetric representation of individual spaces, detects walls, windows and doors between them and
435 splits the PCD into point clusters of individual spaces from large-scale cluttered PCDs of complex
436 environments.

437 We showed that the proposed method reduces modelling efforts when using state-of-practice
438 semi-automated modelling tools. However, the method has the potential to improve other ap-

439 proaches for geometry digitisation, as mentioned above. Future research will concentrate on
440 adopting this method to enable fully automatic gDT construction. This includes combining it with
441 existing methods for smaller object detection, room-scale PCD processing and relation detection
442 methods, as proposed above. Another research direction includes adopting state-of-the-art neural
443 networks to reduce the influence of furniture in extremely cluttered spaces and to separate open
444 spaces adjacent rooms and corridors, as the method currently struggles with them. Lastly, we will
445 properly evaluate the performance of the proposed method on multi-storey buildings and correctly
446 manage covered ceilings and ceilings with baffles.

447 The proposed method reduces the manual effort necessary for digitising existing buildings. As
448 a result, DTs of old assets become cheaper to construct. This reduces the price of operation and
449 maintenance of such assets through various benefits of DTs shown in the previous research and
450 in current industry practices. This entails cheaper operation of buildings and, therefore, a better
451 economy.

452 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

453 Some or all data, models, or code generated or used during the study are available in a repository
454 online in accordance with funder data retention policies at <http://buildingparser.stanford.edu/dataset.html>.

456 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENT**

457 This work is funded by the EU Horizon 2020 CBIM project under agreement No. 860555 and
458 EU Horizon 2020 Bim2Twin project under agreement No. 958398.

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TABLE 1. Navigable transitions (doors and windows) detection performance.

Area	Precision	Recall
1	95.83	97.87
2	96.97	96.97
3	77.78	100.0
4	97.5	100.0
5	92.16	100.0
6	97.67	100.0
S3DIS Avg	92.99	99.14
TUM	75.51	100.0

TABLE 2. Transitions within the same space detection performance.

Area	Precision	Recall
1	100.0	89.47
2	100.0	100.0
3	100.0	75.00
4	100.0	100.0
5	100.0	85.71
6	100.0	100.0
S3DIS Avg	100.0	91.70
TUM	100.0	91.67

TABLE 3. Wall detection performance.

Area	Precision	Recall
1	97.50	95.12
2	88.89	96.00
3	81.08	93.75
4	83.51	92.05
5	85.95	97.20
6	95.00	97.94
S3DIS Avg	88.66	95.34
TUM	81.25	95.12

TUMCMS	dataset 1	dataset 2
Pan et al. (Pan et al. 2023)	93.72	92.66
Ours	97.94	96.72

TABLE 4. Average IoUs on TUMCMS dataset.

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(a) Non-Manhattan Layouts.

(b) Complex ceiling shapes.

(c) Large-scale.

Fig. 1. Key benefits of the proposed method.

(a) Bay window.

(b) Dormer window.

Fig. 2. Complex space shapes near windows. Author Viktor Drobnyi.

Fig. 3. Method overview.

Fig. 4. Example for void detection in 2D.

Fig. 5. Transition features.

(a) Large scale.

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Fig. 6. Two-scale empty space detection. Initially detected empty space is in green, and newly detected empty space is in red. The ceiling is removed for visualisation purposes.

(a) Clustering.

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Fig. 11. Example of false positive detection of walls on corners. Blue bounding boxes are true positive extended bounding boxes of walls, orange bounding boxes are false positive extended bounding boxes of walls.

Fig. 12. Resulted point clusters of detected spaces painted in distinct colours.

Fig. 13. Intersection over Union for spaces for S3DIS dataset. It shows the percentage of detected spaces with a higher IoU than a threshold.